

An investigation into the effects of organisational culture on employee performance at the Oshana Regional Council, Namibia

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to investigate the effects of organisational culture on employee performance at Oshana Regional Council (ORC), Namibia. Mixed research methods were used to collect, analyse and interpret data from respondents and key informants. Participants of the study consisted of 103 employees of Oshana Regional Council. Questionnaires and face to face interviews were used to collect quantitative and qualitative data respectively. The Statistical Program for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 was used to compute the quantitative data while descriptive and inferential statistics were applied to better understand its meaning. To examine the association between employee performance and organisational culture at Oshana RC, methodological triangulation was utilized to strengthen the credibility and validity of the findings. The study found that a Hierarchical Culture is the dominant culture at Oshana Regional Council. It was the finding of this study that the Hierarchical Culture is relatively weak and ineffective in driving employee performance. It was also established that employee performance is positively influenced by organisational culture. The study concluded that a strong organisational culture can provide a number of benefits including organisational unity of purpose, behaviour control and it improves employee commitment. The study recommended that ORC managers should use leadership styles that are most suited to their situation in order to achieve high productivity and should periodically conduct cultural audits.

Keywords: Organisational culture, employee performance, organisation, corporate, organisational performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Oshana Regional Council is a Regional Authority, the second layer of government authority in Namibia. On August 31, 1992, Oshana Regional Council was founded under Section 2 (1) of the Regional Councils Act, 1992. The mandate of Oshana Regional Council, according to its Strategic Plan (2017: p.1) is to plan and administer the region's socio-economic development. Accountability, inclusiveness, responsiveness, transparency, professionalism, and innovation are values that the regional council aims to live by. However, besides having such a key mandate of delivering key services to its people, ORC was not functioning to the best of its capability and capacity and the outcry from the general public was that the Council should improve on its service delivery.

Martins and Martins (2003) advise that in order to understand how an organisation works, one must investigate the effectiveness of the organisational culture and how it supports employee performance. The way in which an organisation operates has been variably defined as organisational culture (OC). According to Julie (2016), OC is a set of values that influence how employees perform their jobs. Needel (2004) posits that culture encompasses all aspects of the organisation. Goke (2015) as cited in (Maxwell & Chukwudi, 2018) points out that culture embraces organisational values, norms, work habits (performance), leadership styles and reward systems.

Oshana Regional Council has a great mandate which if fulfilled can bring prosperity to the people of Namibia, but this is not the case.

1.2 Problem Statement

By influencing how we interpret the world around us, organisational culture provides a potent mechanism for shaping behaviour. Organisations don't live in a vacuum; they are part of a culture or socio-cultural milieu that shapes how their people think, feel, and act. Organisational culture has a significant impact on an employee's day-to-day activities (Maxwell & Chukwudi, 2018). According to Julie (2016), employee performance in many organisations across the world has dropped over the last decade. When opposed to private companies, government institutions have a history of redundancy. According to the 2019 human resource annual report of Oshana Regional Council, employee turnover has been increasing, the Council's performance declined by 25%, and according to the 2020 annual report, the Council's performance further dropped by 40%. So far, empirical evidence from diverse research on the effects of organisational culture on business performance has shown mixed, inconclusive, and inconsistent conclusions. In their study, Lok and Crawford (2004) cited in Awadh and Saad (2013) discovered that organizational culture had a favourable impact on employee performance. Mahmudah (2012) found a substantial association between organisational culture and delivery of services. Jiddah, Rayyan, and Umar (2016) on the other hand, claim that there is almost no evidence to support the impact of organisational culture on employee performance. Although there has been a lot of research done on the impact of corporate culture on employee performance, there is still some debate and studies have not yet established a rational link between company culture and employee performance. Empirical literature of evidence-based studies have yielded diverse results about the effects of organizational culture on employee job effectiveness and competence. It is in this regard that the subject of whether organisational culture promotes or degrades employee performance warrants additional investigation. The objective of this study was to contribute to the body of knowledge by investigating the effects of organisational culture on employee performance at the Oshana Regional Council, Namibia.

1.3 Research Objectives

The main objective of this study was to investigate the effects of organisational culture on employee performance at Oshana Regional Council. The sub-objectives were:

- 1.3.1 To investigate the dominant organisational culture at the Oshana Regional Council.
- 1.3.2 To determine the influence managers, have on successful crafting of organisational culture.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Meaning of Corporate or Organisation

According to Kotter (1992), cited in Li (2015), stated that corporate is a late 15th century term derived from the Latin word '*corporatus*,' which means 'to form into a body.' '*Corpus*' is a Latin term that signifies 'body.' Corporate now refers to a collection of persons who can be handled as a single entity for administrative purposes, which explains its use in the corporate world (Li, 2015). To put it in another way, Kotter & Heskett (2010) argue that the term corporate refers to a business corporation or a specific company corporation.

2.2. Employee Performance and Organisational Culture

Employee performance, according to Evans (2016) is described as how successfully a person performs his or her job, obligations, and responsibilities. In the interest of fairness and transparency, the measure of employee performance used should ideally be transparent to the employee, with performance objectives and standards made plain to the employee from the start (Noel, 2012). Kreitner, Kinicki & Cole (2007) as cited in Evans (2016) in their works "Fundamentals of organizational behaviour", state that the function of organisational culture is to provide employee identity in an organisation, provide collective convenience, promote social system stability, and shape employee behaviour. In their works they further note that, organisational culture has a significant impact on practically every area of the organisation's operations. The study asserts that employee engagement and, ultimately, employee performance are heavily influenced by organisational culture within an organisation. Organisational culture has an influence on workers and their job satisfaction, managers and their life styles and strategies adopted by organisations to achieve their objectives. Many authors measure employee performance using the following indices: productivity, employee commitment, punctuality innovation etc. Employee productivity is a measure of the output of a worker for a given quantity and quality of input. It is a type of input/output analysis designed to evaluate how a single unit of input is transformed by worker into the expected output (Julie, 2016).

2.3 Types of Cultures

The following cultures were outlined by Cameron & Quinn (2011):

2.3.1 Bureaucratic Culture

The Bureaucratic Culture prioritizes internal hierarchical integration. In a controlled and structured work environment, this can be evident in a culture where leaders serve as coordinators, monitors, and organisers. This culture believes that having controls, capable procedures, and efficiency are the key to achieving organisational success.

2.3.2 Clan/Consensual Culture

This culture is defined by tradition, loyalty, personal dedication, thorough socialisation, teamwork, self-management, and societal influences (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

2.3.3 Entrepreneurial Culture

High levels of risk-taking, enthusiasm, and inventiveness describe an Entrepreneurial Culture. Experimentation, innovation, and staying ahead of the curve are all priorities (Cameron & Quinn, 2011). Furthermore, this culture supports flexibility, but instead of teamwork, it emphasizes dynamism and an entrepreneurial aptitude with a visionary and innovative thrust in a leader.

2.3.4 Market/Competitive culture.

This culture is competitive, results-oriented, and externally orientated. It focuses mostly on customers and leaders. Its worth is determined by market share, profitability, and objective achievement (Cameron & Quinn, 2011).

2.4 The Role of Culture in the Organisation

Cited in Li (2015), Brown (1995) indicates that culture encourages dispute resolution. In addition, culture promotes coordination and control. Moreover, when a difficult decision must be made, organisational culture may even assist in narrowing the range of options to examine. A company's culture reduces ambiguity and organisational culture can be a significant source of employee motivation. As a result, culture has a significant impact on the efficiency and performance of the organisation. A good corporate culture might give an organisation a head start in terms of competitive advantage; because it encourages consistency, coordination, control, and reduces anxiety while increasing motivation and facilitating organisational effectiveness.

2.5 Theoretical Framework

This study was based mainly on the Denison organisational culture model. Other theories discussed are; Schein's theory of organisational culture and Hofstede's Manifestation of Culture.

2.5.1 Schein's three-level model

According to Schein (2010), direct mechanisms such as behaviour, staff standing, and opinions, among others, have a direct impact on corporate culture. The purpose and vision of a corporation, rules and regulations, corporate identity, rituals, and designs are all examples of indirect mechanisms that influence organisational culture. To this goal, Schein (2010) proposed a three-level description that includes artefacts, values, and underlying principles, as shown below:

Figure 1: Schein's three-level model of corporate culture is seen in the above figure. Source: think-boundless.com

Logos, corporate apparel, structures, processes, artefacts and architecture are all examples. This is visible to all stakeholders and marks the organisation's surface (Schein, 2010). Espoused values are the second culture, which focus on setting standards, principles and a codes of conduct. The fourth culture mentioned by Schein (2010) is basic underlying assumptions.

2.5.2 Denison Organisational Culture model

Denison's study resulted in the creation of a model that focuses on four criteria that have been linked to organisational effectiveness: Mission, adaptability, consistency, and involvement.

Source: Denison (2011, p.23), organizational culture

Figure 2: Denison organisational culture model.

According to Denison (2011), the assessment instrument is designed to identify organisational culture and how it affects performance. Figure 2 depicts the four characteristics that are closely associated to organisational effectiveness, according to Denison (2011). The underlying aspects of corporate culture, mainly beliefs and assumptions, are depicted at the centre of the diagram.

According to Denison (2011) mission describes the direction in which the organisation is headed; it examines issues such as the company's strategy, vision, goals, and objectives. Adaptability, on the other hand, provides information on how well the organisation allows the demands of the business architecture or the external environment to influence operations. Focusing on the client and for example, bringing about change, promotes both growth and survival, and this is linked to a learning company that strives for sustainability through its adaptability. The third is involvement theory which focuses on determining whether the organisation's people are aligned, in this theory, collaboration is centred on continual empowerment, with efficacy and building capacities at its foundation. Last but not least is the consistency theory, this is based on the organisation's basic principles and guarantees that a well-coordinated structure is poised to get things done.

Whereas measuring the model is challenging, the Denison culture model was created to attract attention to the soft features, which should be highlighted in culture and performance assessment as organisational diagnosis takes place. For instance, if the Council receives a poor grade on empowerment under the involvement theory, a debate among the leadership team may conclude that employees want empowerment training. Denison argues in this sub-mission that training employees on empowerment may not yield the anticipated benefits, owing to other underlying influencing variables. According to Denison (2011), a low ranking on empowerment could be ascribed to low morale and a lack of trust from employees toward management

2.5.3 Hofstede's Manifestations of Culture

Simelane (2017) cites Hofstede et al (1990) who categorise cultural manifestations into four groups: symbols, heroes, rituals, and ideals (as indicated in Figure 3). Within a society, symbols are words, gestures, visuals, or things that have a specific significance. Heroes are people, living or dead, real or imagined, who possess culturally valued attributes and consequently serve as role models for others (Wilkins, 1984 as cited in Simelane, 2017). Rituals are group actions that are technically unnecessary but socially important within a culture, and might be considered to be performed for their own purpose. According to Hofstede (1990), as cited in Simelane (2017), these layers are analogous to the successive skins of an onion, progressing from shallow surface symbols to deeper rituals. Symbols, heroes, and rituals can all be categorised as practices since they are visible to an observer, but their cultural significance depends on how it is understood by insiders.

Figure 3: Manifestations of Culture: From Shallow to Deep Source (1980). Adapted from Hofstede

2.6 Empirical Review

The link between organisational culture and performance has been studied by many scholars. Organisational culture is an important component of organisational success and a source of competitive advantage according to Sharma and Good (2013). Correspondingly, employee performance is favourably connected with organisational culture, according to Weedrathna and Greenganage (2014). Strong organisational cultures, according to these academics, are effective vehicles for outstanding employee performance.

Ojo (2011) investigated numerous organisational culture concepts to determine the significance of its relationship with corporate performance in the business context. According to the findings of the study, organisational culture has a significant impact on an organisation's overall success. Similarly, Aluko (2013) investigated the association between organisational culture and employee performance, and discovered that a weak culture causes an organisation's employees to perform poorly and collaborate ineffectively. According to Shahzad (2012) an examination of a large body of literature revealed that organisational culture has a significant impact on a number of organisational processes, personnel, and performance. Burnes (2009:p.128) agrees with the foregoing, stating that 'culture is at the heart of competitive advantage, particularly when it comes to maintaining high performance'. According to Burnes (2009) in his Bain and Company report, approximately 70% of business leaders feel that culture is the most important source of competitive advantage. Likewise, Immordino (2010:p.84) recommended that it is important to create an organisational culture that encourages high-quality practices and that motivates people to achieve high-performance. Kawooya (2010) conducted a study on the impact of leadership styles on employee performance. The Research adopted survey design, while the sampling technique was simple random sampling. The study sampled the opinion of 280 respondents using a questionnaire. The data was sourced through primary and secondary sources and results showed that there is a negative association between authoritative leadership and employee performance.

According to the study by Kawooya (2010), authoritative leadership has a negative impact on individual performance, reducing the efficiency of individual innovativeness and creativity at work. On the other hand, employee performance and democratic leadership style were found to have a beneficial link in the study. Correspondingly, Chan & Chong (2014) investigated how leadership styles affect employee commitment. The questionnaire was adopted to sample the opinion of 384 respondents from a retail industry in China. A convenience sampling method was adopted. Their study revealed that democratic leadership style has a substantial beneficial association with employee performance.

Maxwell & Chukwudi (2018) examined the influence of organisational culture on employee performance. The research approach included a sample of 300 employees from four bottling factories in eastern and southern Nigeria utilizing a combination of judgmental and basic random techniques, with a structured questionnaire as the data collection instrument. For correlations and analysis of variance, the primary data were analyzed using version 20 of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). According to the study's findings, an organisation's culture has a considerable impact on employee performance. Employee performance was measured in terms of commitment, productivity and punctuality, while culture was measured in terms of leadership style and reward system. Democratic leadership style had a 50.2 percent impact on employee productivity, commitment and punctuality. Employee productivity, commitment and timeliness are all affected by the same situation.

A critical review of organisational culture on employee performance was conducted by Narayana (2017). Employee engagement and performance were investigated as a result of company culture. Questionnaire were distributed to 251 respondents from 9 government bank branch offices and Malang Regional offices. According to the findings, employee engagement and performance positively influenced by organisational culture. However, other researchers have found that the association between numerous cultural traits and employee performance have changed through time (Denison, 2015).

2.7 Conceptual Framework

A conceptual framework is a visual or textual product that "explains, either graphically or in narrative form, the primary objects to be studied; the key components, concepts, or variables and the hypothesized relationships among them", (Weeraratna & Geeganage, 2014:24). Organisational culture is the independent variable while employee performance is the dependent variable in order to determine the link between organisational culture and employee performance at the Oshana Regional Council. The overwhelming direction of effect is demonstrated by the direction of the pointed arrows in Figure 4:

Source: *Researchers own work*

Figure 4: Conceptual Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Philosophy

This study, employed a pragmatic approach as a research philosophy because pragmatism uses both positivism and interpretivism (Creswell, 2013). Additionally, as a philosophical viewpoint, pragmatism sees knowledge as a necessary fact or an intimate experience.

The population of this study was 140 employees as per the Oshana Regional Council’s staff establishment (2021). The population had 59 male and 81 female members and among the population of 140, there were 6 managerial employees. Using Krejcie & Morgan (1970) sampling table, a sample size of 103 was found appropriate for the study. Purposive non-random sampling technique was used for the qualitative study responses. Interviews consisted of key informants made up of purposively selected managers and these were six (6) in number. To obtain quantitative data, structured-questionnaires were used.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

97 completed questionnaires were returned achieving a response rate of 94%. Of these respondents 56% (53) were female and 44% (47) were male. Females outnumbered males in this sample, according to the findings. This is a true reflection of the employment statistics at Oshana where the total employment demographics show that there are more female employees than males.

4.1 Analyses of Research Objective 1: To investigate the dominant organisational culture at the Oshana Regional Council.

Figure 5: Dominant existing Culture at ORC

The above graph indicates that Council is made up of a mix of the four cultures, with each culture's score fluctuating in strength. According to the findings, out of 97 respondents 46.47 percent of respondents stated that the Council was a very controlled and organised environment, (Hierarchy Culture) and that is the major existing organisational culture at ORC. Of the 97 respondents, (26) 27 percent stated that the ORC organisational culture to be results-oriented (Market Culture). 19% of the participants found the ORC culture to be personal (Clan Culture). The vibrant and entrepreneurial atmosphere (Adhocracy Culture) at ORC was the least popular with 7% in favour. Furthermore, only 79.4% of the respondents (see Table 1 below) agreed that existing culture (Hierarchy Culture) influences employee performance. Of those who reported that the ORC is very results oriented (Market Culture) 96.1% of them indicated that ORC culture influences performance as shown in table 4.2 below.

Table 1: Existing Culture influences performance at ORC

Existing Culture at ORC	Organisational culture influence performance		Total
	Yes	No	
ORC is a very personal place (Clan Culture)	12 (15.6%; 66.7%)	6(30%; 33.3%)	18
The organisation is a dynamic entrepreneurial place (Adhocracy Culture)	6 (7.8%; 85.7%)	1(5%; 14.3%)	7
ORC is results oriented (Market Culture)	25(32.5%; 96.1%)	1(5%; 3.9%)	26
The organization is a controlled and structured place (Hierarchy Culture)	34(44.2%; 73.9%)	12(60%; 26.1%)	46
Total	77(79.4%)	20(20.6%)	97

4.2 Analysis of Research Object 2: To analyse the effectiveness of Oshana Regional Council’s organisational culture

The 5-point Likert Scale was used to indicate the respondents’ level of agreement with various statements on characteristics of organisational performance based on questions derived from Denison four theories of measuring organisational culture namely: Involvement theory, Consistency theory, Adaptability theory and Mission theory. Figure 6 – 9 below present the effects of organizational culture on employee performance at Oshana Regional Council.

4.3 Involvement Theory

The results are illustrated in figure 6 above. Under this theory, three key performance areas were considered for this study. These are empowerment, team work, and capability development. 74% of the respondents agreed that there is team work at ORC as a result, it would be appropriate to state that ORC's culture is team-oriented and participative. This instance

demonstrates that teamwork can survive even in a bureaucratic or high-power-distance culture like ORC. Omukuga (2017), Salihu, Salihu & Musa (2016) and Saad & Abbas (2018) have all found that collaboration improves performance. In addition, 68% participants agreed that they are empowered at the ORC. Only 49% agreed on capability development at the ORC and 29% disagreed. Thus, this co-variable (capability development) needs to be looked at and targeted interventions should be addressed to this group to create a conducive environment for employees at ORC. In summary the respondents agree that there is high rate involvement theory at the ORC.

4.4 Consistency Theory

The outcomes are shown in figure 7 above. Three main performance areas were selected for this study based on consistency theory, these are core values, agreements, and coordination and integration. For core values, 59% of the respondents agreed that ORC's executives and managers follow through on their promises, there is a clear and consistent set of values that governs ORC's operations, and the Council is on track with its purpose and vision. 58% of the respondents are in agreement with the consistency theory. When disagreements arise at ORC, employees work together to address common problems and achieve common goals. As a result, they work tirelessly to find win-win solutions. Participants were asked whether they agreed with how good the atmosphere is and how easy it is to coordinate projects across various sections at ORC. 64% were in agreement with coordination and integration as shown in figure 4.8 above.

4.5 Adaptability Theory

Three performance areas were measured under adaptability theory as shown in figure 8 above. The co-variables tested to quantify success under adaptation theory were creating change, customer relations, and organisation development. 65% of respondents interviewed agree that customer focus and organisational learning contribute to adaptability theory respectively. The 65% respondents in agreement feel that customer's inputs directly influence ORCs decision-making; policies and procedures helps ORC provide services according to customer wants and needs; Failure is viewed as a chance for learning and improvement by the council, and learning is an essential goal in ORC's day-to-day operations. Only 56% of the respondents agreed that creating change, while 30% were indecisive and 14% did not agree.

4.6 Mission

Mission and vision are important components of corporate culture because they impact on employee behaviour and direct the many operations that will be carried out in the firm. Under the Mission theory, three key performance areas were considered for this study. These are strategic direction, goals & objectives and vision. The results illustrated in figure 9 above reveal that 75% of the participants agreed that goals and objectives are present at the ORC followed by 69% who agreed that there is a strategic direction at ORC. Furthermore, only 61% agreed on vision at the ORC and 14% disagreed. In summary the respondents agree that the Mission at the ORC is well understood. Under this performance category the following were measured: The ORC has a distinct mission that provides meaning and purpose

4.7 Employee performance

The outcomes are shown in figure 10 below. Four main performance areas were selected for this study based on employee performances. Punctuality, Leadership, Reward system and Communication were the co-variables studied to measure employee performances

4.7.1 Punctuality

Punctuality is one of the most essential aspects in determining an individual's performance and ability to keep their job. 48% of the respondents agreed that punctuality contributes to employee performance, and if tasks are normally completed on schedule and workers achieve time related organisational goals. 30% of the respondents were indecisive while 17% respondents disagree that punctuality contributes to employee performance.

4.7.2 Leadership

Omukuga (2017) claims that an organisation's culture is shaped by the type of leadership it has. A culture of learning and sharing information is fostered by a leadership style that displays mentorship and support. 56% of the respondents agreed that mentoring, facilitation, and nurturing are all qualities that the Oshana Regional Council exemplifies. Further indicated that management contributes to the positive culture of ORC and management style influences performance. 26% of the respondents were indecisive while 17% respondents disagree.

4.7.3 Reward System

Participants were asked if they believed that employee incentives increased their engagement and how it affects employee turnover. The reward system at the ORC did not show positive results/contribution to employee performances. 51% of respondents did not agree that the council has clear reward procedures (promotions, gifts, awards); nor are employees aren't compensated based on how well they do on the job. Only 33% of the respondents agreed that the reward system contributes to employee performance and the other 16% of the respondents were indecisive.

4.7.4 Communication

Communication is an essential component of any culture since it encourages the dissemination of core business values, beliefs, and practices. Communication of mistakes was discovered to be a crucial statement in the study, as shown in figure 4.7, in order to make employees feel valued and appreciated. Employees have timely and accurate information to advise policy and decision makers, according to 54% of respondents. Mistakes and weaknesses are communicated in a respectful and non-threatening manner. 24 percent, on the other hand, were not convinced. Employees expressed their dissatisfaction with the lack of respect and politeness with which they were treated. They expressed their dissatisfaction with the lack of politeness with which errors were corrected.

4.8 Testing for Association using Chi-square

Table 2: Chi-Square

	Chi-Square	Sig. Level (0.05)
Empowerment	27.485	.000
Team Work	54.082	.000
Capability Development	32.742	.000
Core values	31.299	.000
Agreements	60.784	.000
Coordination & Integration	63.979	.000
Creating change	17.186	.001
Customer Focus	36.557	.000
Organizational Learning	49.959	.000
Strategic Direction	50.577	.000
Goals and objectives	75.32	.000
Vision	49.649	.000
Punctuality	14.907	.005
Leadership	36.351	.000
Reward System	7.278	.122
Communication	40.165	.000

The Chi-Square Test of Independence analysed whether categorical variables were associated (i.e., whether the variables were independent or related). It is a test that is not parametric. The data is analysed using a contingency table in this test. A contingency table (sometimes called a cross-tabulation, crosstab, or two-way table) is a data classification system that uses

two categorical variables. The total number of cases for each pair of categories is represented in each cell. Table 2 above presents the results of Chi-square. The results show an association between the following variables testing at 0.05 level of significance; empowerment, team work, capability development, core values, agreements, coordination & integration, creating change, customer focus, organizational learning, strategic direction, goals and objectives, vision, punctuality, leadership and communication. The only variable whose null hypothesis of association was accepted is the reward system with p-value of 0.122 greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus there is statistical evidence of lack of association between other performance variables and the reward system.

4.9 Multinomial Logistics Regression

The multinomial logistic regression model is an extension of the binary one (A binary logistic regression model is a generalized linear model which used to computes the probability of the selected response as a function of the values of the independent variables), with several levels rather than dichotomous outcomes (Mood, 2010). According to Sperandei, (2014) the dependent variable (Y) is used to model the link between a polychromous response variable or multi category answers and a set of independent variables or to forecast the likelihood of categorical response variables. This study considered all employee performances variables to see if they influence other categories. Odd ratio (OR) and 95% Confidence Intervals were used to test likelihood/chances that employee performance variables affect other variables.

When there are several explanatory variables, logistic regression is used to calculate the odds ratio. With the exception that the response variable is binomial, the approach is quite similar to multiple linear regression (Sperandei, 2014). The key benefit is that it eliminates confusing effects by examining the relationship between all variables.

Table 3: Employee performance based on punctuality

Employment performance based on punctuality	Sig.	OR	95% Confidence Interval for OR	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Core values	.140	3.304	.675	16.177
Agreements	.115	.292	.063	1.348
Coordination and Integration	.776	.792	.159	3.944
Creating Change	.373	.483	.097	2.397
Customer Focus	.440	.021	.459	6.014
Organizational Learning	.002*	.068	.013	.367
Mission	.853	1.139	.287	4.515
Empowerment	.0001*	1.661	.012	.171
Team work	.127	4.131	.667	25.580
Capability Development	.025*	6.576	1.271	34.041

a. The reference category is: Strongly Disagree. * p < 0.05

Table 3 above displays employee performance based on punctuality for respondents who strongly agreed with those who strongly disagreed as a reference category. The results illustrate that only three variables were significant in the model, which are organizational learning, empowerment and capability development whose p-values were all less than 0.05 level of significance. Furthermore, the results show that respondents who strongly agreed on capability development (OR = 6.576, 95% C.I = (1.271; 34.041)) were 6.5 times more likely to be influenced by punctuality than those who strongly disagree, holding constant all other variables. Empowerment (OR = 1.661, 95% C.I = (0.12; 0.171)) is 66.1% higher when influenced by punctuality for those who strongly agreed. For those who strongly agreed on organizational learning, the odds of being influenced by punctuality is 93.2% lower [i.e. (1-0.068)*100] as compared to those who strongly disagree holding constant all other variables.

4.10 Analysis of objective 3: To determine the influence managers, have on successful crafting of organisational culture.

Table 4: Employee Performance based on Leadership

Employee Performance based on Leadership	Sig.	OR	95% Confidence Interval for OR	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Empowerment	.584	.598	.095	3.757
Team work	.977	1.042	.062	17.562
Capability Development	.253	.248	.023	2.712
Core values	.887	1.139	.189	6.872
Agreements	.737	.709	.095	5.268

Coordination and Integration	.399	.382	.041	3.576
Creating Change	.239	.228	.019	2.678
Customer Focus	.802	1.226	.249	6.038
Organizational Learning	.201	3.428	.519	22.634
Strategic Direction	.380	2.810	.280	28.181
Goals and Objectives	.030*	.027	.001	.700
Vision	.293	3.219	.364	28.435
The reference category is: Strongly Disagree. * p < 0.05				

The results Table 4 shows that only one variable was significant in the model, which is Goals and Objectives whose p-value was less than 0.05 level of significance. For those who strongly agreed on goals and objectives, the odds of being influenced by leadership is 97% lower [i.e. (1-0.030) *100] as compared to those who strongly disagree holding constant all other variables.

Table 5: Employee performance based on Reward System

Employee performance based on Reward System	Sig.	OR	95% Confidence Interval for OR	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Empowerment	.188	.154	.009	2.498
Team work	.562	.445	.029	6.899
Capability Development	.015*	34.262	2.014	582.725
Core values	.407	.423	.056	3.229
Agreements	.138	3.168	.691	14.533
Coordination and Integration	.728	1.580	.120	20.751
Creating Change	.030*	.178	.037	.850
Customer Focus	.196	2.373	.640	8.805
Organizational Learning	.539	.588	.108	3.200
Strategic Direction	.278	.239	.018	3.169
Goals and Objectives	.122	.118	.008	1.767
Vision	.598	.643	.125	3.317
The reference category is: Strongly Disagree. * p < 0.05				

Table 5 compares respondents who strongly agreed with those who strongly disagreed as a reference category in terms of job performance based on reward system. Only two variables were found to be significant in the model holding constant all other variable, which are: capability development and creating change. Furthermore, the results show that respondents who strongly agreed on capability development (OR = 34.26, 95% C.I = (2.014; 582.725)) were 34.26 times more likely to be influenced by the reward system than those who strongly disagree, holding constant all other variables. Creating change (OR = 0.178, 95% C.I = (0.037; 0.850)) is 17.8% lower when influenced by reward system for those who strongly agreed holding constant all other variables

Table 6: Employee performance based on communication

Employee performance based on communication	Sig.	Exp (B)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp (B)	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Empowerment	.057*	.239	.055	1.044
Team work	.043*	7.016	1.059	46.496
Capability Development	.801	1.160	.367	3.668
Core values	.005*	.181	.055	.602
Agreements	.008*	.134	.031	.590
Coordination and Integration	.212	.397	.093	1.694
Creating Change	.854	.863	.179	4.168
Customer Focus	.007*	.111	.022	.550
Organizational Learning	.520	1.576	.394	6.306
Strategic Direction	.037*	9.212	1.139	74.504
Goals and Objectives	.477	.525	.089	3.097
Vision	.137	3.318	.683	16.112
a. The reference category is: Strongly Disagree. * p < 0.05				

Table 6 above shows employment performance based on communication for respondents who strongly agreed with those who strongly disagreed as a reference category. The results demonstrate that six variables were significant in the model, which are empowerment, team work, core values, agreements, customer focus and strategic direction, whose p-values were all less than 0.05 level of significance. Furthermore, the results indicate that respondents who strongly agreed on Empowerment (OR = 0.239, 95% C.I = (0.055; 1.044)) had 23.9% lower odds to be influenced by communication than those who strongly disagree, holding constant all other variables. Teamwork (OR = 7.016, 95% C.I = (1.059; 46.496)) is 7 times higher when influenced by communication for those who strongly agreed holding constant all other variables.

4.11 Section B: Presentation of findings & Discussions of Qualitative Data

Interviews were conducted with 4 Managers who became the study's key informants; Manager A, Manager B, Managers C, Manager D. None of the managers agreed to be tape-recorded.

4.11.1 Theme 1: How do you understand the concept of organisational culture at the ORC.

On interviewees, different views of the concept of organisational culture emerged. Manager B and C, view the concept as sets of standards and practices of the company and the employees embrace it as the main guide to their output.

4.11.2 Theme 2: The most dominant Culture at ORC and how effective it is?

The results of the qualitative data suggested that Hierarchy Culture was the extent prevalent trait of the Oshana Regional Council.

One key informant narrated that:

"The council's current culture is exceedingly regimented and controlled. What people do here is often governed by formal protocols."

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study's broad goal was to investigate the effects of organisational culture on employee performance at the Oshana Regional Council.

5.1 Summary of Findings

Literature evaluated for this study agreed that the four types of organisational culture were Bureaucratic Culture, Clan/Consensual Culture, Entrepreneurial Culture, and Market/Competitive Culture. Furthermore, the literature indicated that many scholars, researchers and academics have examined the link between organisational culture and performance and came out with various findings. There was no consensus in the findings of earlier researchers. The aspects that make up an organisation's culture are values, beliefs, philosophy, leadership styles, and reward system. Strong organisational cultures, according to the literature assessed for this study, are great drivers for outstanding employee performance. Likewise, the review found that a poor culture causes an organisation's and its personnel to perform poorly and collaborate ineffectively, resulting in a lack of involvement, consistency, adaptability, and mission. Organisational culture, as a social construct, influences employee behaviour in the workplace.

5.2 Summary of findings from quantitative data

According to the qualitative study findings, the most prevalent culture at the Oshana Regional Council is Hierarchical Culture. It was also found that hierarchies control and govern employee behaviour, as well as the amount to which they make decisions. However, the Hierarchical Culture has little impact on staff performance at the Council, as the majority of respondents said the culture was ineffectual, indicating the need for a more flexible and effective culture. The study found that managers have a significant role to play when it comes to crafting an organisational culture that fosters success. The majority of respondents agreed that the organisation's leadership exemplifies mentoring, facilitation, or nurturing. Employees also confirmed that they received feedback from senior managers and their supervisors. According to the findings, 54% of respondents agreed that mistakes and weaknesses are shared in a respectful and non-threatening manner, and employees have timely and accurate information to assist policy and decision-makers. According to the conclusions of the study, hierarchies control and govern employee behaviour, as well as the amount to which they may make decisions. The study findings reveal that organisational culture enabled internal integration and coordination between different departments.

5.3 Summary of findings from qualitative data

According to the qualitative study findings, the most dominant culture at the Oshana Regional Council is Hierarchical Culture. In addition, based on the qualitative study findings, the Council is not having proper communication channels, most of the interviewees indicated that in order to create a work culture as a supportive drive for performance the council needs to enhance its communication procedures. Furthermore, the goal of this research was to determine the type of link that exists between ORC's corporate culture and employee performance. According to the findings of this qualitative study, organisational culture is positively linked to employee performance. These findings are in line with earlier research that suggests organisational culture variables are predictive of both organisational and personnel performance. The study further revealed that the organisational culture at ORC helps in adopting harmonious employee relationships that lead to effective organisational performance.

5.4 Recommendations

The study came up with the following recommendations:

- 5.4.1 ORC should strengthen its organisational culture as this will lead to improved employee performance.
- 5.4.2 ORC should conduct cultural audits twice a year to determine whether the organisation's culture is still relevant and whether corporate values are shared among employees.
- 5.4.3 The study recommended that ORC managers should adopt leadership styles that are most suited to their employees for high productivity.
- 5.4.4 There should be adequate funds set aside by the organisation to support production so that employees achieve their performance targets.

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